

A Model of Travelling Waves in the Neural Medium with Directional Variability of Inhibitory Effects

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Abstract. In the present study we test the hypothesis on a radially asymmetric spread of evoked cortical traveling wave corresponding to the stimulation of the median nerve. We employ the theory of neural fields to derive a mathematical model of traveling waves where a parameter related to recurrent inhibitory connections in the neural field and, hence, the traveling wave speed are directionally dependent. We combine this model with the anatomical model of the subject cerebral cortex (obtained by MRI) for the reconstruction of the traveling wave corresponding to the experimental MEG and find the approximation error in the space of MEG sensors. We compare this result with the MEG simulation based on the assumption that the traveling wave spread is radially symmetric and demonstrate the advantage of the former modeling approach by assessing the results of the two approximations. We also illustrate the results of the two approximations by graphical presentation of the dynamics of electric potentials on the anatomical model of the subject neocortex.

Keywords: neural field models, cortical traveling waves, evoked neural activity, asymmetric traveling wave, evaluation of traveling wave parameters

Acknowledgements: The present research is supported by the Russian Science Foundation (Project No 23-11-20020, <https://rscf.ru/en/project/23-11-20020/>)

Introduction

Localization and reconstruction of current sources from electroencephalography (EEG) and magnetoencephalography (MEG) signals in neuroscience is a complex problem, and its solution has the potential to significantly enhance our understanding of the processes related to electrical activity in the brain. This process can be useful in a number of different application tasks [1, 2, 3] such as disease detection, neural decoding, brain–computer system development, and numerous others.

In a recent article [4] the authors introduced an approach based on the use of an Amari-type neural field equation for modeling of traveling waves of electric potentials in the neocortex. The results of simulations of travelling waves were compared with the MEG

signal corresponding to the stimulation of the median nerve together with another simulation based on the use of trigonometric functions. Both simulations demonstrated high values of correlation with the experimental data. However, the approach based on neural field theory allowed to connect the parameters of the traveling wave (such as the shape of its spatial profile and the wavespeed) to the parameters having physiological interpretations (such as the interneuronal connections topology description and the values of neuronal activation thresholds). The study relied on the assumption that the spread of neuronal excitation from the epicenter is radially symmetric [5]. In the present research we test the hypothesis on directional variability of the inhibitory effects in the process of spread of a travelling wave from the epicenter in the neural medium, which may cause directionally non-uniform spread of the traveling wave. In order to do that instead of assessing the similarity between the simulated and the experimental signals using their correlation, we measure this similarity based on a "difference" between the measured and the simulated signals as functions of spatial and temporal variables in an appropriate functional space.

The paper is organized as follows. In Sect. 2 we suggest a mathematical model of traveling waves we use in the testing of our main hypothesis and define our computational approach for the comparison of the simulated and the experimental signals. In Sect. 3 we describe the results of the comparison. Concluding remarks are given in Sect. 4.

1. Mathematical Formalism

Following the ideas of [4, 6, 7, 8], we consider Amari neural field equation with a mechanism that limits the excitation in the neuronal medium:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u(t, x) &= -u(t, x) + \int_R \omega(t, x) f(u(t, y)) dy, \\ \frac{1}{\epsilon} \partial_t v(t, x) &= u(t, x) - \sigma v(t, x), \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

$$t \geq 0, \quad x \in R, \quad \sigma > 0, \quad 0 < \epsilon \ll 1.$$

Here $u(t, x)$ represents the level of electrical activity of the neural field at time t and the position x , the function ω defines the strengths of interneuronal connections in the neural field, the value $f(u)$ determines the probability of activation (firing) of a neuron with electrical activity level u . In the mathematical neuroscience community, the connectivity ω is typically assumed to be an exponentially decaying function symmetric with respect to the vertical axis or a sum of such functions, and a probabilistic activation function f is naturally taken to be a sigmoidal function (see e.g. [6]). The component v is the negative feedback which is slow with respect to the rate of the excitation processes in the neural field (i.e. $\epsilon \ll 1$). The negative feedback decay is determined by the constant σ that we refer to as a relative strength of the inhibitory effects in the neural medium. The relative strength σ of the inhibitory effects in the neural field can be characterized as follows: an increase in the value of σ corresponds to a reduction of the inhibitory effect strength.

The work [4] relied on the hypothesis that the spread of traveling waves from the epicenter is radially symmetric, which means that $u(t, x) = u(t, r, \varphi) \equiv u(t, r)$ where (r, φ) are the

polar coordinates in the two-dimensional neural field ($r > 0$, $0 \leq \varphi < 2\pi$). Our approach suggests that the relative strength of the inhibitory effects σ is not constant with respect to the angular (directional) variable φ , i.e. $\sigma = \sigma(\varphi)$.

Proceeding in the way analogous to [4, 8, 9], we substitute a Heaviside-type activation function instead of the sigmoidal activation function in order to get a closed-form expression of a traveling wave solution to (1), i.e. $f(u) = H(u)$, where

$$H(u) = \begin{cases} 0, & u \leq h, \\ 1, & u > h, \end{cases}$$

with some constant $h > 0$, that plays the role of neuronal activation threshold in the neural field.

A function u is a traveling wave with speed c if $u(t, x) = U(x - ct)$, where the waveform U of the traveling wave u satisfies the following conditions:

- $U(x) > h$ on $(0, a) \subset R$
- $U(x) < h$ on $R \setminus [0, a]$.

Assuming that $f = H$ and $\sigma = \sigma(\varphi)$, the wavefront U has the form

$$U(r, \varphi) = -\frac{1}{c} \int_{-\infty}^r k(r - \rho, c, \varphi)(W(\rho) - W(\rho - a))d\rho \quad (2)$$

where

$$W(y) = \int_0^y \omega(\xi)d\xi,$$

$$k(r, c, \varphi) = l_2 \exp(\lambda_2(\varphi)r) - l_1 \exp(\lambda_1(\varphi)r),$$

$$l_1(\varphi) = -\frac{p_{11}(\varphi)p_{22}(\varphi)}{p_{11}(\varphi)p_{22}(\varphi) - p_{12}(\varphi)p_{21}(\varphi)}, \quad (3)$$

$$l_2(\varphi) = -\frac{p_{12}(\varphi)p_{21}(\varphi)}{p_{11}(\varphi)p_{22}(\varphi) - p_{12}(\varphi)p_{21}(\varphi)},$$

$$\lambda_1(\varphi) = \frac{1 - \epsilon\sigma(\varphi) - \sqrt{1 - \epsilon\sigma(\varphi) - 4\epsilon}}{2c},$$

$$\lambda_2(\varphi) = \frac{1 - \epsilon\sigma(\varphi) + \sqrt{1 - \epsilon\sigma(\varphi) - 4\epsilon}}{2c},$$

$$p_{1j} = \frac{(\epsilon\sigma(\varphi) - 1) - (-1)^j \sqrt{(\epsilon\sigma(\varphi) - 1)^2 - 4\epsilon}}{2\epsilon}.$$

Numerical realization of the concept of directionally variable relative strength of the inhibitory effects is implemented by the identification of 36 radial directions (uniform sectors

of 10 degrees) in a small vicinity (about 2 cm) of the epicenter of the traveling wave propagation. We set an individual relative strength σ of the inhibitory effects in each sector to solve the problem of finding the wave propagation speed. Thus, in each of the sectors we reconstructed the values of the wave speed c and strength of the inhibitory effects σ based on the formalism (2). Following the ideas of [10, 11], we naturally treat the waveform function (2) and the respective traveling wave solution as a function continuous in the temporal and spatial variables. Using a modification of the neural field equations, we reconstruct the current distribution on the triangulated surface of the cerebral cortex initiated by a traveling wave at time t and calculate the direct MEG problem using the direct matrix G [12]. Thus, we transfer the values of the Amari model into the values of the magnetic field vector strength on the sensors. Then we assess the deviation of the simulated travelling wave from the experimental MEG signal. We also uniformly discretize the time interval of 100 ms by 120 points and sum the aforementioned deviations in the space of sensors over the temporal mesh to find the total error of the approximation. The reconstruction of the values of σ and c was based on the minimization of the total error of the approximation as a function of σ and c .

2. Results

We used the materials of the Brainstorm tutorial [12] in our modeling. Evoked MEG signals were recorded by stimulating the right median nerve. The source of the evoked activity was identified in the left hemisphere. The forward problem was addressed by placing current dipoles on the vertices of the triangulated individual anatomical surface of the brain. The epicenter of the traveling wave of the initial high-amplitude component was identified in earlier research [4].

To compare the simulation results (Fig. 1), we used experimental data of 0-100 ms from the beginning of stimulation. When comparing the full 100-ms segments, the mathematical model correlated at the level $r = 0.43$. Comparison with the first component of the evoked MEG showed the maximum correlation $r = 0.98$. Thus, taking into account the directional variation of the traveling wave parameters in the cerebral cortex helped to improve the results of MEG signal modeling compared with the approach of modeling a homogeneous traveling wave spread [4].

In Fig. 2, the distribution of the reconstructed quantities σ and c over the 36 angular sectors is shown. Under the assumption of a uniform individual relative strength σ of the inhibitory effects, the reconstructed values of this parameter and the traveling wave speed are $c = 0.22$ (m/s), $\sigma = 0.12$. The total errors of the approximations are 9.69 and 0.11 in the cases of simulated MEG for the uniform and directionally varied relative strength of the inhibitory effects, respectively, which clearly demonstrates the validity of the latter hypothesis on the traveling wave spread.

A video demonstrating the propagation of the reconstructed traveling wave of electrical activity on the anatomical model of the subject cerebral cortex is available via the link <https://disk.yandex.ru/d/pjsJrO5knwNxA>. The video allows to compare the propagating traveling waves in the following two cases:

- simulated MEG for a uniform relative strength σ of the inhibitory effects,
- simulated MEG for a directionally varied relative strength σ of inhibitory effects.

Рис. 1. (a) Experimental MEG 100 ms with the clipped first high-amplitude evoked component 23.3–50.8 ms from the beginning of the stimulus; (b) Simulated 100 ms MEG without directional variation in σ ; (c) Simulated 100 ms MEG with directional variation of the reconstructed traveling wave speed c and relative strength σ . The green line represents the global field power (GFP), i.e. the standard deviation of all the sensors values from the zero-level at each time point.

One of characteristic pictures from this video ($t = 65$ ms from the start of the traveling wave spread) is given in Fig. 3.

3. Discussion

The modification of the Amari model used in this work demonstrates better results in the MEG modeling compared to the approach suggested in [4], as evidenced by a high correlation between the experimental and the simulated signals. The advantage of the proposed model, which was demonstrated by the computation of the total errors of the experimental MEG approximations, was based on the assumption that the propagation of a traveling wave due to intracortical connections occurs asymmetrically, i.e. the speeds of "intracortical communication" between neurons differ in different directions due to a directional variation of the inhibitory effects. These effects may be caused e.g. by a microstructure of the neocortex (various mathematical formalizations of this microstructure can be found e.g. in [13, 9, 14]). A modeling of asymmetric waves was carried out in the analysis of sources of epileptic activity in [15]. Unlike our simulation, the base waves were calculated using the sine function in this study. Our model relies on the mathematical theory of neural fields, which allows us to evaluate physiological parameters (e.g. the strength of recurrent inhibitory connections) in relation to anatomical landmarks. This additional information can be valuable in the analysis of EEG and MEG.

4. Ethical Approval

In our work, we used the data set of the resource <https://neuroimage.usc.edu/brainstorm/Tutorials/MedianNerveCtf>. This data set belongs to the MEG Lab, McConnell Brain Imaging Center, Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Canada. The authors of this data set are Elizabeth Bock, Esther Florin, Francois Tadel and Sylvain Baillet. The data is distributed freely with the indication of authorship.

Рис. 3. Reconstructed traveling waves on the anatomical model of the subject cerebral cortex: (a) directional variation in σ ; (b) directional variation in σ (smoothened cortex); (c) directionally uniform σ ; (d) directionally uniform σ (smoothened cortex). The arrows serve connections between the subfigures (a), (b), and the diagram in Fig. 2.

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